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Acronyms and Abbreviations

BIA	BiImage Archive
IDR	Image Data Resource
SSBD	A platform for Systems Science of Biological Dynamics
INSDC	International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration
wwPDB	Worldwide Protein Data Bank
REMBI	Recommended Metadata for Biological Images
FBbi	Biological Imaging Methods Ontology
NCBITaxon	NCBI organismal classification
CLO	Cell Line Ontology
CL	Cell Ontology
UniProt	Universal Protein Resource
ChEBI	Chemical Entities of Biological Interest Ontology
EFO	Experimental Factor Ontology
OBI	Ontology for Biomedical Investigation
UO	Units of Measurement Ontology
SNOMED CT	Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine-Clinical Terms
CMPO	Cellular Microscopy Phenotype Ontology
UBERON	Uberon Multi-species Anatomy Ontology (Uber-anatomy Ontology)
GO	Gene Ontology
MeSH	Medical Subject Headings
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
ROR	Research Organization Registry
CRedit	Contributor Role Taxonomy
4DN	4D Nucleome

BINA	Bioluminescence Imaging North America
OME	Open Microscopy Environment
QUAREP	Quality Assessment and Reproducibility
NGFF	Next-generation file format
RRID	Research Resource Identifier
PIDInst	Persistent Identification of Instruments
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
DOID	Disease Ontology
MONDO	Mondo Disease Ontology
HPO	Human Phenotype Ontology
ICD	International Classification of Diseases
NEUBIAS	Network of European BioImage Analysts
GloBIAS	Global BioImage Analysts' Society
OBO	Open Biological and Biomedical Ontologies
OxO	Ontology Xref Service
NCBO	National Center for Biomedical Ontology
SQL	Structured Query Language
RO-Crate	Research Object-Crate

Table of contents

Acronyms and Abbreviations	2
Table of contents	4
Executive Summary	5
1. Introduction	6
2. Metadata Comparison and Analysis	6
2.1. Metadata Components	7
2.2. Ontologies and Controlled Vocabularies	8
3. Requirements for Metadata Harmonization	10
3.1. Anticipated Use Cases	10
3.2. Survey of Ontologies and Controlled Vocabularies	11
3.2. Proposal of Metadata Harmonization Requirements	12
4. Toward Metadata Harmonization	13
4.1. Phased Approach to Harmonization	13
4.2. Additional Considerations for Harmonization	14
4.3. Methods for Sharing Metadata	14
5. Acknowledgements	15
6. References	15

Executive Summary

The purpose of this report is to define the metadata harmonization requirements across various data resources to enhance the interoperability of bioimaging data. To achieve this, we first compared the metadata models of the major bioimaging data resources – BioImage Archive (BIA), Image Data Resource (IDR), and SSBD:database – to identify overlaps and differences of metadata components, as well as to determine the metadata components and ontologies that should be harmonized. Next, we analyzed various use cases for bioimaging data reuse, identifying the necessary metadata components, suitable ontologies, controlled vocabularies, and relevant communities to clarify the requirements for metadata harmonization that would facilitate data reuse. Finally, we provided milestones for BIA, IDR, and SSBD to achieve metadata harmonization for global bioimaging data sharing. Additionally, we briefly explored metadata management and sharing methods to consider a more sustainable and flexible framework for bioimaging data integration.

1. Introduction

Nucleotide sequence data and protein structure data have already established frameworks for data sharing and integration, widely used through repository networks such as the [International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration](#) (INSDC; Karsch-Mizrachi et al., 2012) and the [worldwide Protein Data Bank](#) (wwPDB; Berman et al., 2003). By adopting common metadata schemas and standardized annotations, these datasets enable researchers to efficiently search for data and facilitate interoperability across different databases. This standardization has streamlined data integration across institutions and projects, globally, further promoting applications in fields such as machine learning and AI-based analysis.

Similarly, the need for a global data-sharing framework for bioimaging data has been recognized (Swedlow et al., 2021). However, the development of such a system for bioimaging data remains insufficient compared to nucleotide sequence and protein structure data. Bioimaging data, including microscopy images, pre-clinical images, and pathology images, are generated using a diverse range of imaging instruments and analytical techniques, resulting in heterogeneous formats and metadata descriptions. Consequently, data reuse and integrative analysis remain challenging, and ensuring interoperability across different research projects presents a significant hurdle. Establishing standardized metadata framework is essential to enhance data interoperability and facilitate seamless data sharing across the bioimaging community.

Just as with nucleotide sequence data and protein structure data, there is an increasing demand for a metadata-driven framework that enables data sharing across bioimaging data resources. Enhancing interoperability among different data resources is expected to improve analysis accuracy and facilitate new scientific discoveries. However, one of the significant challenges in managing and sharing bioimaging data is the rapid increase in data size. Recent advancements in microscopy and live imaging technologies have led to experiments generating image datasets on the scale of hundreds and gigabytes to terabytes. Given this scale, integrating all data into a single data resource is impractical due to limitations in storage capacity, data transfer speed, and the diverse operational requirements of different repositories. Instead, it is essential to harmonize metadata components and unify controlled vocabularies to enable efficient data search, retrieval, and integration.

This report aims to compare and analyze the metadata models of existing bioimaging data resources to identify key differences and challenges, as well as to propose the requirements for metadata harmonization to achieve greater interoperability. Here we will investigate major bioimaging data resources – [BioImage Archive](#) (BIA; Hartley et al., 2023), [Image Data Resource](#) (IDR; Williams et al., 2017), and [SSBD:database](#) (Kyoda et al., 2025) – by analyzing the overlaps and differences in their metadata models to propose the requirements for metadata harmonization. Furthermore, we will explore methods for metadata sharing across these data resources and discuss future directions for data sharing and integration.

2. Metadata Comparison and Analysis

To facilitate seamless cross-resource search and data integration, it is essential to compare the metadata descriptions and components used across different data resources, identifying both similarities and differences. In this report, we conducted a comparative analysis of metadata models used in the following three bioimaging data resources:

1. BioImage Archive (BIA) – <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-archive/>
2. Image Data Resource (IDR) – <https://idr.openmicroscopy.org/>

3. SSBD:database (SSBD) – <https://ssbd.riken.jp/database/>

The BIA is a public bioimaging data repository and maintained by EMBL-EBI. The IDR is an added-value public database developed and maintained by the University of Dundee. The SSBD:database is another added-value public database developed and maintained by RIKEN.

We examined the metadata model structure and components employed in these data resources, analyzing their similarities and the controlled vocabularies and ontologies used.

Table 1: Application and comparison of metadata components from BIA, IDR, and SSBD to the REMBI¹

Module	Attribute	Details	BIA	IDR	SSBD	
Study	Identity	unique ID	uuid_accession_id	Id	SID	
	Study type	Study type				
	Study description	Study description				
	General dataset info	authors	authors	author:	Publication Authors	person:
		publication	publication	title, doi, pubmed_id	Publication Title/DOI	paper info, DOI, PubMed ID
	license	license	license	License	license	
	release date	release date	release_date	Release date	date of released	
Study Component	Imaging Method	Imaging Method	fbbi_method_type	Imaging Method	imaging method:	
	Study component description	description	description		description	
Biosample	Identity	internal unique ID	uuid		(strain)	
	Biological entity	biological entity	biological_entity			
		Cell Line			cell_lines	cell line
		Cell Type				cell
		Pathology		Pathology		
	Organism	organism	organism_classification	organism	organism	
	Intrinsic variable	Intrinsic variable	intrinsic_variables			intrinsic variable
		Gene			Gene	gene
	Extrinsic variable	Extrinsic variable	extrinsic_variables			extrinsic variable
		Compound			Compound	reagent/compound
Antibody				Antibody	reagent/compound	
siRNA				siRNA	(oligo primer)	
Experimental variables	experimental_variables	experimental_variables		experimental variables		
Specimen	Experimental status	Experimental status				
	Location within Biosample	Location within Biosample				
	Preparation method	specimen_preparation_method	{method, growth_control}_description		preparation method	
	Signal/contrast mechanism	Signal/contrast mechanism	signal_contrast_mechanism_description			
	Channel - content	Channel - content	channel_content_description	ChannelInfo:	tag	
	Channel - biological entity	Channel - biological entity	channel_biological_entity	ChannelInfo:	(protein)	
Image acquisition	Instrument attributes	Instrument	imaging_instrument_description	Instrument:	instruments:	
	Image acquisition parameters	acquisition method	acquisition_method			
Image data	Identity	unique ID	uuid	id	ID	
	Type	Type				
	Format & compression	format	image_format		file format	
	Dimension extents	dimension	size_(x, y, z, c, t)	Size(X,Y,Z,C,T)	dimensions	
	Size description	data size	total_size_in_bytes		file size	
	Pixel/voxel size description	pixel/voxel size	physical_size_(x, y, z, t)	PixelSize(X,Y,Z),TimeIncrement	{X, Y, Z, T}scale	
	Channel information	channel	channel_(content_description, biological_entity)	ChannelInfo:	tag, protein	
	Image processing method	Image processing method	annotation_method			
	Contrast inversion to TEM	Contrast inversion to TEM				
	QC info	QC info				
	Image Correlation	Spatial and temporal alignment	Spatial and temporal alignment			
		Fiducials used	Fiducials used	fiducials_used		
		Transformation matrix/other info	Transformation matrix/other info	transformation_matrix		
Related images and relationship	Related images and relationship					
Analysed data	Analysis result type	type	method_type			
		Phenotype		Phenotype		
	Data used for analysis	Data used for analysis	annotation_file:		Source	
Analysis method and details	Analysis method and details	annotation_method:		Workflow		

2.1. Metadata Components

Metadata components were extracted from BIA, IDR, and SSBD and mapped to detailed categories defined in the [REMBI](#) (Recommended Metadata for Biological Images; Sarkans et al., 2021) guidelines (Table 1). The REMBI guidelines organize recommended metadata for bioimaging data. In this analysis, by mapping the metadata components of BIA, IDR, and SSBD to the detailed attributes of

¹ All tables in this document are also available on Zenodo for citation: [\[doi:10.5281/zenodo.15549859\]](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15549859).

REMBI, it is expected that the overlaps and differences in metadata content can be visualized, contributing to improved interoperability among the resources.

Twelve metadata components, *Study identifier, authors, publication, license, release date, imaging method, organism, channel – content, channel – biological entity, Data identifier, dimension, and pixel/voxel size*, were found to be overlapped across all three models. This indicates that these metadata components are considered fundamental and indispensable information in each model.

Additionally, while some metadata components were not present in all models, many were shared between multiple models (Table 1). These shared components, though selectively incorporated based on the design and purpose of each model, likely possess a certain level of standardization and versatility, playing a crucial role in enhancing interoperability across different models.

On the other hand, each model also contained unique metadata components that were not present in the others. These components appear to be tailored to the specific characteristics and applications of the respective data resources. Therefore, when comparing or integrating metadata, it is crucial to consider not only shared components but also model-specific metadata and explore how they can be mapped or transformed for integration.

The comparative analysis of metadata components only considered aligning them based on their similarity to the definitions of attributes found in REMBI. However, inherent hierarchical structures between the objects significantly impact data organization and interpretation, so a detailed structure comparison is also required.

As an example, examining the hierarchical placement of specific metadata components, we observed differences in how Organism (Species) information is structured across the models.

- BIA and SSBD place Organism metadata under the Study Component in REMBI.
- IDR includes Organism metadata at a higher hierarchical level, corresponding to Study in REMBI

This distinction likely arises from IDR's focus on high-content screening datasets and reference datasets for the same organism, making species information applicable to the dataset as a whole. In contrast, BIA and SSBD accommodate datasets involving multiple species, leading them to associate species information at the Study Component in REMBI.

These findings highlight the importance of considering the hierarchical structure of metadata components when considering interoperability between different data resources. Differences in metadata placement across hierarchies arise from the distinct purposes and scopes of each data resource. While this study does not perform a detailed analysis at that level, it is crucial to recognize that challenges may emerge when implementing cross-search functionality and other integrative approaches. A deeper understanding of metadata structures and their organization will be essential for developing effective mapping and integration strategies in future research, ultimately contributing to improved metadata standardization and interoperability.

2.2. Ontologies and Controlled Vocabularies

A key factor in achieving interoperability for bioimaging data shared across BIA, IDR, and SSBD is the use of ontologies and controlled vocabularies to represent metadata. In this section, we compare the controlled vocabularies used in the metadata models of these three data resources (Table 2).

It was found that controlled vocabularies and ontologies for species ([NCBITaxon](#)) and imaging methods ([FBbi](#)) are commonly used across all three models. This indicates that these controlled vocabulary and ontology are widely recognized and established as standard terminologies in the bioimaging field. On the other hand, while not universally adopted by all three models, certain controlled vocabularies are shared by multiple models, suggesting that these vocabularies play a crucial role in enhancing interoperability between different data resources.

Table 2: Comparative analysis of ontologies and controlled vocabularies used in BIA, IDR, and SSBD

Category	Ontology/Controlled vocabulary	Acronym	BIA	IDR	SSBD
Imaging Method	Biological Imaging Methods Ontology	FBbi	✓	✓	✓
Taxonomy	NCBI Organismal Classification	NCBITaxon	✓	✓	✓
Cell Line	Cell Line Ontology	CLO			✓
Cell type	Cell Ontology	CL			✓
Gene	Ensembl	ENSG		✓	✓
	Entrez Gene	NCBI_Gene		✓	
Protein	Universal Protein Resource	UniProt		✓	✓
Chemical Compound	PubChem	PubChem		✓	
	Chemical Entities of Biological Interest Ontology	ChEBI			✓
Experimental Condition	Experimental Factor Ontology	EFO		✓	✓
	Ontology for Biomedical Investigation	OBI			✓
Unit	Units of Measurement Ontology	UO			✓
Disease	Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine-Clinical Terms	SNOMED CT		✓	
Cellular Phenotype	Cellular Microscopy Phenotype Ontology	CMPO		✓	
Anatomy	Uberon Multi-species Anatomy Ontology	UBERON			✓
Biological Process	Gene Ontology	GO			✓
Cellular Component					✓
Molecular Function					✓
Controlled Vocabulary	Medical Subject Headings	MeSH			✓

Ontologies can fulfill multiple roles, such as serving as controlled vocabularies, providing data schemas, or specifying rules and constraints. However, our analysis revealed that BIA, IDR, and SSBD currently use controlled vocabularies with limited hierarchical structure rather than embracing complex Ontology Web Language (OWL)-based descriptions or constraints. One primary reason is the extreme diversity of imaging-related metadata, which makes it impractical to adopt a monolithic ontology with elaborate axioms. Instead, repositories generally rely on these common terms as a semantic tag for annotation that provides a baseline of mutual understanding.

Additionally, there are instances where different controlled vocabularies are used for the same metadata components, such as genes and compounds. This variation arises due to the unique objectives and contexts of each model, reflecting differences in the criteria for selecting controlled vocabularies. For example, IDR uses [PubChem](#) to cover a wide range of drug screening reference datasets, as it focuses on sharing datasets related to drug compound treatment. In contrast, SSBD prioritizes ontology-based accuracy and hierarchical structure, opting for [ChEBI](#), which provides a high-quality representation of chemical substances. In such cases, it is necessary to establish precise mappings between different controlled vocabularies and implement mechanisms that link them effectively. Defining mapping rules or creating conversion tables between vocabularies could help ensure data consistency across different models and enable seamless data sharing.

Furthermore, it should be noted that some controlled vocabularies require specific licenses for use. For instance, [SNOMED CT](#) is one of the most widely used terminologies in the medical field across various countries. However, in Japan, its usage is restricted due to licensing constraints. As a result, models that adopt SNOMED CT must establish appropriate linkage mechanisms with alternative controlled vocabularies that are available in Japan. Taking such licensing constraints into account, selecting appropriate controlled vocabularies for each country and domain and developing frameworks to interconnect them will be essential for facilitating data integration.

3. Requirements for Metadata Harmonization

We have compared the metadata models of BIA, IDR, and SSBD, analyzing overlapping and model-specific components. These metadata components play a crucial role in connecting different data resources and ensuring harmonization. However, considering the future reuse of bioimaging data, it is also necessary to identify additional metadata components that should be shared beyond those currently included. Therefore, based on various use cases for bioimaging data, we will identify metadata components to be shared and integrate them into a recommended metadata framework.

In designing the recommended metadata, it is essential to clarify how users intend to utilize the data. By properly defining use cases, we can establish precise metadata requirements, ensuring that researchers can efficiently access the information they need.

3.1. Anticipated Use Cases

By considering various use cases, a comprehensive metadata framework can be constructed to accommodate diverse user needs.

- 1 Use cases related to data retrieval and search
 - 1.1 Search based on publications and public information
 - Searching for publication-related data: *Publication, Authors, Organization, Study Unique ID*
 - Searching for the latest data: *Release Date*
 - 1.2 Search based on imaging technology and instrument
 - Specific imaging methods and techniques: *Imaging Method, Instrument*
 - Specific dimensions and resolution: *Dimension, Pixel/Voxel Size, Time Interval*
 - 1.3 Search based on biological subjects
 - Organisms and cell lines: *Organism, Cell Line*
 - Genes and proteins: *Gene, Channel – Biological Entity*
 - Compounds, antibodies, probes, and tags: *Compound, Antibody, Channel – Content*
 - 1.4 Search based on pathology, phenotype, and tissue
 - Search by pathology/disease: *Pathology, Disease (Biological Entity)*
 - Search by phenotype: *Phenotype (Analysis Data)*
 - Search by organ and tissue: *Organ*
- 2 Use cases related to data comparison and integration
 - Evaluating data quality and reproducibility: *Instrument, Imaging Method*
 - Integrating data under different experimental conditions: *Study Unique ID, Dataset Unique ID, Study Description, Pixel/Voxel Size, Time Interval*
 - Multi-modal hierarchical integration with other datasets: *Gene, Compound, Phenotype*
- 3 Use cases related to data identification, management, and usability enhancement
 - Referencing and tracking research data: *Study Unique ID, Dataset Unique ID*
 - Tracking data relationships and processing history: *Study Unique ID, Dataset Unique ID, Publication*
 - Automated extraction and annotation of metadata: *Study Description*
- 4 Use case related to data analysis
 - 4.1 Quantitative analysis of pathology images
 - AI-driven automated classification and screening of cancer tissues: *Pathology, Disease (Biological Entity), Organ*

- Quantification of biomarker expression levels from immunohistochemistry images: *Pathology, Disease (Biological Entity), Organ, Channel – Content*

4.2 Automated annotation of large-scale data

- Machine learning-based automated labeling of cells and tissues: *Analyzed Data*
- Development of standardized workflows for large-scale data annotation, enabling benchmarking across different algorithms and datasets: *Analyzed Data*

3.2. Survey of Ontologies and Controlled Vocabularies

Next, we conducted an investigation into ontologies and controlled vocabularies that can be used to represent the metadata components identified above. In addition to the ontologies and controlled vocabularies already used in BIA, IDR, and SSBD, we explored other relevant vocabularies and communities that should be considered.

- 1 Standardization of researcher and organization information
 - [ORCID](#): A globally recognized identifier for uniquely identifying researchers, useful for managing dataset authorships.
 - [ROR](#): An international repository for identifying research institutions, aiding in the unified management of data-providing institutions.
 - [CRedit](#): A standardized framework that categorizes author contributions in academic research into 14 distinct roles.
- 2 Standards for imaging and bioimaging data
 - [EDAM Bioimaging](#): A standard for describing bioimaging data formats and processing methods, contributing to improved data reusability.
 - [4DN-BINA-OME-QUAREP](#): A framework aimed at standardizing imaging acquisition and processing protocols to enhance data reproducibility.
 - [OME-NGFF](#): A next-generation file format for bioimaging data, influencing metadata embedding and management methods.
 - [BioSample](#): A standardized schema for managing metadata of biological samples, ensuring consistent annotation, including geographic locations.
 - [RRID](#): A unique identifier for research resources such as cell lines, antibodies, model organisms, and tools, ensuring data transparency and reproducibility.
 - [PIDInst](#): A Persistent Identifier (PID) standard for identifying research instruments, relevant for recording metadata about microscopes and other instrument.
- 3 Standard format for time and date
 - [ISO8601](#): An international standard for consistency formatting dates and times, applicable to metadata components such as timestamps and publication dates.
- 4 Ontologies related to diseases and phenotypes
 - [DOID](#): A structured ontology of human diseases, useful for recording disease information consistently in metadata.
 - [MONDO](#): An ontology integrating multiple disease ontologies, facilitating the standardization of disease information across repositories.
 - [HPO](#): A structured ontology of human phenotypes, useful for linking disease and genetic data in metadata
 - [ICD-11](#): The international classification of diseases provided by WHO, widely used as a medical classification system, contributing to metadata standardization.
- 5 Image analysis-related communities

- [NEUBIAS](#): An international community focused on best practices and standardization in image analysis, potentially influencing metadata management for image data.
- [GloBIAS](#): An initiative aiming for international standardization of biological image analysis, potentially contributing to defining standard metadata requirements for image analysis.

The listed ontologies, controlled vocabularies, and imaging/image analysis communities were selected based on their active engagement in the field. The development and maintenance of ontologies and controlled vocabularies require domain expertise and continuous curation. Given the rapidly evolving nature of bioimaging technologies, conducting this work solely within this project is impractical. Therefore, we aim to collaborate with established ontology communities, such as [OBO Foundry](#), and reuse existing ontologies and controlled vocabularies to enhance interoperability through stable identifiers and well-defined schemas.

3.2. Proposal of Metadata Harmonization Requirements

Based on these findings, we propose a metadata harmonization framework that establishes shared metadata components and their representations using ontologies and controlled vocabularies to connect bioimaging data resources.

Table 3 provides the recommended components for metadata harmonization. These components are structured based on metadata adopted by major bioimaging data resources, while also considering use case alignment to ensure that researchers can quickly access the necessary information.

Table 3: Requirements for metadata harmonization (components and their representation)

Component	Description	Format	Access Query
Study Description	Description of the study	Text	Free text
Authors	Information about the authors	First name and Last name; Affiliation, ORCID	Author name, ORCID, ORCID, ORCID, Organization name, ROR
Organization	Information about the organization	Name URL, ROR	Name, ROR
Publication	Information on the related publication	Text (Title), Publication year, DOI (Journal)	DOI
License	Information about the dataset's license	Creative Commons with the version and URL	CC version, URL
Release Date	The release date of the data	ISO 8601 format (including time/time zone)	Release date, range search
Imaging Method	The method used to obtain image data	FBBI, EDAM Bioimaging Ontology term and ID	FBBI or EDAM Bioimaging Ontology ID, term
Cell Line	Information about the cell line	Cell Line Ontology term and ID	CLO ID, term
Organism	Information about the organism studied	NCBI Taxonomy term and ID, BioSample (geographic location)	NCBI Taxonomy ID, term
Gene	Information about related genes	Ensembl Gene or NCBI Gene name or ID	Gene ID, name
Compound	Information about the compound	CHEBI or PubChem term and ID	Compound ID, term
Antibody	Information about the antibody used	FBBI or CHEBI term and ID, RRID	Antibody ID, term
Channel – Content	Content related to the channel	FBBI term and ID	Channel content ID, term
Channel – Biological Entity	Biological entities related to the channel	Experimental Factor Ontology term and UniProt ID	Biological entity ID, term
Instrument	Information about the instrument used	Compliant with 4DN-BINA-OME-QUAREP (NBO-Q) standards, PIDInst	Instrument name, ID
Dimension	Information about data dimensions	Compliant with OME-Zarr axes info. (T, C, Z, Y, X)	Dimension specification
Pixel/Voxel Size/Time resolution	Size of the pixels or voxels, Time interval	Pixel/Voxel size and time interval stored with units	Pixel/voxel size, Time interval
Study Unique ID	Unique ID for the study	Accession ID, DOI	Accession ID, DOI
Dataset Unique ID	Unique ID for the dataset	Accession ID	Accession ID
Pathology/Disease (Biological Entity)	Pathology/Disease related to the biological entity	SNOMED-CT, DOID, ICD-11 or MONDO	Pathology/Disease ID, term
Phenotype (Analysis Data)	Phenotypic data related to the analysis	Cell Morphology Phenotype Ontology, MPO, or HPO	Phenotype ID, term
Organ	Information about anatomical entities	UBERON, RadLex Ontology	UBERON ID, term
Analyzed Data	Information about software, workflow, annotation data	GitHub URL (release), DOI (Zenodo, Figshare), RRID, Dataset ID	Name, DOI

4. Toward Metadata Harmonization

4.1. Phased Approach to Harmonization

To achieve metadata harmonization among BIA, IDR, and SSB, it is essential to define clear phases and proceed step by step. Since each data resource's metadata model is designed based on its

objectives and operational policies, attempting to unify them all at once is not feasible. Instead, a phased approach should be taken to gradually adjust and align the metadata.

In the first phase, the goal is to identify metadata components that are commonly adopted across all data resources and unify their descriptions and vocabularies. For instance, metadata components such as biological species and imaging methods, which are used across all data resources, should adopt shared ontologies and controlled vocabularies. This standardization would enhance the accuracy of searches and integrated analyses across different data resources. By establishing this uniformity, researchers will be able to more easily search and utilize data across different data resources.

The second phase focuses on addressing metadata components that are shared among multiple data resources but use different ontologies and controlled vocabularies. For example, IDR uses PubChem for chemical compound representation, while SSBD adopts ChEBI. In such cases, it is necessary to clarify the correspondences between these controlled vocabularies and establish a mapping mechanism that enables interconversion. Additionally, for terminologies such as SNOMED CT, which are subject to licensing restrictions in certain countries, alternative open vocabularies (e.g., MONDO/DOID) should be linked to ensure broader usability. Tools such as [OxO](#) (Ontology Xref Service), [NCBO BioPortal](#), and [TogolD](#) can be leveraged to facilitate ontology and vocabulary mapping, with the scope of application expanded progressively in each phase.

The third phase involves organizing metadata components unique to each data resource and determining how they should be integrated. Each data resource includes specific metadata components tailored to its purpose, and simply unifying them may not always be appropriate. Therefore, it is crucial to classify components that require standardization and those that should remain unique to each resource and apply suitable management methods to each. Furthermore, metadata components that are not currently included in existing data resources but would be useful for data integration should be considered for addition. For instance, in marine biology, the geographic location where a specimen was collected is a crucial piece of metadata. This phase should focus not merely on integration but on designing an approach that enhances data interoperability.

Looking ahead, REMBI offers a flexible framework that can reference a common ontology—or multiple standard ontologies—while allowing each resource to modularize and adapt specific ontological modules or vocabularies for its own needs. This approach provides repositories with greater flexibility in accommodating the myriad data types prevalent in imaging. By leveraging a shared reference ontology under REMBI and then adjusting or extending that vocabulary as required, these resources can maintain the benefits of standardization without being hampered by the complexity of OWL schema.

Thus, progressing toward metadata harmonization requires the establishment of three clear phases: (1) standardizing common components, (2) addressing differences in ontologies and controlled vocabularies, and (3) organizing unique components and introducing new metadata where necessary. By following this structured process, data integration across different resources can be facilitated, ultimately enabling a flexible data management and sharing framework that is well-suited for applications such as machine learning and AI-driven analysis.

4.2. Additional Considerations for Harmonization

Several challenges and opportunities should be considered.

- **Maintenance of Existing Ontologies:** A key concern is the lack of updates to FBbi, which covers bioimaging methods but has been inactive for over three years, with future updates remaining uncertain. Given the rapid advancements in imaging technologies, it is becoming increasingly important to explore alternative resources, such as EDAM or other regularly maintained ontologies, to ensure continued relevance. While FBbi has played a crucial role in the standardization of bioimaging metadata, identifying sustainable approaches for incorporating emerging technologies will be essential moving forward.
- **Interoperability with the Preclinical Domain:** As datasets expand, incorporating metadata for preclinical studies may become necessary. Ensuring interoperability will require aligning these preclinical metadata components with the recommended frameworks discussed here. Additionally, special attention must be given to non-human datasets and their compatibility with clinical terminologies and ontologies, necessitating further exploration of best practices for cross-domain integration.
- **Regular Updates:** To keep pace with scientific and technological advancements, metadata models should undergo regular review and updates. Establishing a clear governance model (and version control mechanism) will be essential for maintaining consistency and interoperability over time.

By addressing challenges such as integrating emerging research areas and ensuring consistent updates in response to changes in reference ontologies, future harmonization efforts can better align with the evolving needs of the bioimaging community and provide more effective support.

4.3. Methods for Sharing Metadata

Thus far, we have discussed the requirements for metadata harmonization in bioimaging data resources. Finally, we will examine the methods for sharing metadata across different data resources and explore future perspectives on interoperability.

Currently, many data resources employ relational management through SQL databases or simple key-value pair structures. However, when considering integration and interoperability across different databases, a more flexible and standardized metadata management system is required.

One potential solution is utilizing [Research Object \(RO\)-Crate](#) for metadata management. RO-Crate is a framework for packaging research data and its associated metadata in a structured JSON-LD format, facilitating metadata exchange between different data resources. The adoption of RO-Crate enables structured documentation of data provenance and experimental information, improving data reusability.

Metadata storage methods are also a critical consideration. Specifically, there is a need to determine whether metadata should be embedded within the data files themselves (e.g., RO-Crate files in OME-Zarr) or managed separately within a database. The file-embedded approach ensures that metadata remains intact when transferring and sharing data, but it can make metadata updates cumbersome. Conversely, managing metadata in a database allows for more flexible searching and updating but presents challenges in integrating metadata across different data resources. A hybrid approach may be appropriate, where metadata about imaging conditions and biological samples is stored within OME-Zarr files, while metadata describing overall experimental structures and repository linkages is maintained within data resources.

In the future, improving the interoperability of bioimaging data will depend on how these technologies are combined and utilized.

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